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Abstract

This work is focused on the chemical characterization of the organic residues preserved in ceramic fragments that are suspected to have been used by the Basque whalers in the period from 16th to 17th Century to store whale oil. The lipid profiling along with the identification of biomolecular markers, makes possible to obtain information on the contents of the vessels and on the transformations undertaken by the organic substances during the burial process. In order to achieve this goal, two complementary analytical techniques, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography - Electrospray Ionization - Quadrupole Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (HPLC-ESI-QToF) and Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS), were used not only to study the archaeological materials but also fresh whale oil products used as reference materials with the aim to detect potential diagnostic biomarkers. HPLC-ESI-QToF was used to identify the triacylglycerols (TAGs) and study their distribution in the various samples, whereas GC-MS provided the fatty acid (FA) profile together with the detection of degradation compounds (dicarboxylic and dihydroxy fatty acids) and biomarkers related to marine commodities (isoprenoid acids). Samples of blubber from 5 different whale species belonging to the genus Balaenoptera (fin, sei and minke whale), Megaptera (Humpback whale) and harbour porpoise (Phocoena) were used as reference materials together with a sample of whale oil of unknown origin. The chemical results confirm the archaeological data regarding the vessels use as containers to store whale oil and indicate the whales from Balaenoptera genus as a source of the oil.

Keywords organic biomarkers; archaeological ceramics; blubber; triacylglycerides; Gas - Chromatography – Mass Spectrometry; High-Performance Liquid Chromatography - Electrospray Ionization - Quadrupole Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry

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1 **GC-MS AND HPLC-ESI-QToF CHARACTERIZATION OF ORGANIC LIPID RESIDUES FROM CERAMIC**
2 **VESSELS USED BY BASQUE WHALERS FROM 16TH TO 17TH CENTURIES**

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12 **Abstract**

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14 fragments that are suspected to have been used by the Basque whalers in the period from 16th to 17th
15 Century to store whale oil. The lipid profiling along with the identification of biomolecular markers,
16 makes possible to obtain information on the contents of the vessels and on the transformations
17 undertaken by the organic substances during the burial process. In order to achieve this goal, two
18 complementary analytical techniques, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography - Electrospray
19 Ionization - Quadrupole Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (HPLC-ESI-QToF) and Gas Chromatography-
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23 samples, whereas GC-MS provided the fatty acid (FA) profile together with the detection of degradation
24 compounds (dicarboxylic and dihydroxy fatty acids) and biomarkers related to marine commodities
25 (isoprenoid acids). Samples of blubber from 5 different whale species belonging to the genus
26 Balaenoptera (fin, sei and minke whale), Megaptera (Humpback whale) and Phocoena (harbour
27 porpoise) were used as reference materials together with a sample of whale oil of unknown origin. The
28 chemical results confirm the archaeological data regarding the vessels use as containers to store whale
29 oil and indicate the whales from Balaenoptera genus as a source of the oil.

30 *Keywords: organic biomarkers, archaeological ceramics, blubber, triacylglycerols, Gas - Chromatography*
31 *- Mass Spectrometry, High-Performance Liquid Chromatography - Electrospray Ionization - Quadrupole*
32 *Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry*

33 **1. Introduction**

34 The research focused on organic residues preserved in archaeological samples has opened new
35 opportunities for the understanding of ancient common practices and traditions related to trade, diet or
36 even cultural rituals. In this context, ceramic containers are the major class of artifact in which organic
37 residues occur, offering a wide source of powerful information concerning pottery use [1]. The porous

38 nature of the ceramics and the strong interactions occurring between the organic compounds and the
39 ceramic matrix have led to the elucidation of the function of thousands of potsherds from different ages
40 and regions of the world [2-9]. Among thousands organic compounds, the analysis of lipids has gained
41 attention of archaeological studies aiming to infer information about the use and environmental source
42 of pottery sherds, human remains, ancient sediments, etc. [10-15]. In fact, it is known that lipids, and
43 specially their diagenetic and catagenetic hydrocarbon products, can remain unaltered in recent and
44 ancient archaeological remains due to their inherent resistance to decomposition in comparison to
45 other compounds such as proteins [10]. Nevertheless, the natural degradation processes of lipids can be
46 accelerated in oxidant environments and at high temperatures, which often occurs in the context of
47 archaeological pottery vessels preservation [16].

48 Marine commodities have played a very important role in the past XVI-XVII centuries in the Basque
49 Country (northern Spain). Fishing or hunting whales was undoubtedly one of the most productive
50 activities in the Bay of Biscay during more than half a millennium [17]. Basque whalers used to sail
51 across the Atlantic Ocean as far as Newfoundland and Labrador, where there is archaeological evidence
52 of more than a ten of Basque whaling stations located along the Gulf of Saint Lawrence. The Red Bay
53 whale station, which UNESCO named a World Heritage Site in 2013, is the most outstanding of all the
54 whale stations where excavation has taken place. Once the whale was captured its fat was melted in the
55 ovens located at the mentioned stations to collect the blubber or oil which was then stored in wooden
56 barrels and transported back to the Basque Country in order to be sold in Spain or in different places in
57 Europe, such as Flanders or England [17-19]. Before the fats were sold, they were stored in particular
58 large ceramic jars in the docks of Basque ports, ready for their distribution. Recent excavations in the
59 Biscayan village of Lekeitio have recovered several jars and ceramic fragments used for this purpose.

60 Marine fats and oils are an important class of unsaturated lipids which are difficult to detect in the
61 organic residues in archaeological pottery [20,21]. They contain high abundances of polyunsaturated
62 fatty acids (PUFAs) but rarely survive in the ceramic vessels as significant components due to the
63 changes in the chemical composition because of degradation processes. Despite these complications,
64 several degradation products have been identified as biological markers in recent studies focused on
65 marine oils and fats in archaeological ceramic samples. ω -(*o*-Alkylphenyl) alkanolic acids with 16-20
66 carbon atoms are known to be formed at cooking temperatures from fatty acids (FAs) of marine sources
67 [2,21,22]. Dihydroxy acids can also be found in extracts of archaeological pottery and are the direct
68 degradation products of Z-monounsaturated alkenoic acids being C_{20:1} and C_{22:1} fatty acids suggestive of
69 seal or whale fats [19,23]. PUFAs can also be oxidized forming dicarboxylic acids, which have been found
70 in slab-lined pits where marine mammal oil was produced [13,24]. In addition, the isoprenoid FAs
71 4,8,12-trimethyltridecanoic acid (4,8,12-TMTD), 2,6,10,14-tetramethylpentadecanoic acid (2,6,10,14-
72 TMPD, or pristanic acid) and 3,7,11,15-tetramethylhexadecanoic acid (3,7,11,15-TMHD, or phytanic
73 acid) are as well important biomarkers of marine products in archaeological ceramics [21-23].

74 In the peer-reviewed literature, analytical methodologies based on gas chromatography-mass
75 spectrometry (GC-MS) [11,15,25-29] and gas chromatography-combustion-isotope ratio mass
76 spectrometry (GC-C-IRMS) [14,30-33] have been applied for lipidic analysis of organic residues in
77 ceramics. Nevertheless, the FA content can also be obtained with the acquisition of the entire
78 triacylglycerol (TAG) profile of the lipid material [34]. In previous investigations High-Performance Liquid
79 Chromatography - Atmospheric-Pressure Chemical Ionization - Mass Spectrometry (HPLC-APCI-MS) has
80 been applied to identify triglycerides in pottery sherds [35,36]. Nevertheless, high resolution
81 chromatographic techniques such as High-Performance Liquid Chromatography - Electrospray Ionization
82 - Quadrupole Time-of-Flight Mass Spectrometry (HPLC-ESI-QToF) has not been widely used for the
83 analysis of the triglyceride profile of the lipid fraction in archaeological ceramic samples, which could
84 provide more accurate information about the structure of the TAGs. The information obtained by HPLC-
85 ESI-QToF, together with the complementary information obtained by more consolidated analytical
86 techniques such as GC-MS would allow identifying the oils and fats stored in archaeological vessels.

87 Specific extraction, saponification and derivatization steps are required before the chromatographic
88 analyses. Evershed et al. used solvent extraction of the powdered potsherd with a mixture of
89 chloroform/methanol using ultrasonication [30], Ribechini et al. performed the direct saponification of
90 the organic residues found in ceramic pieces with a subsequent extraction step [26], whereas Correa-
91 Ascencio et al. developed a direct acidified methanol extraction [14]. Different derivatization procedures
92 have also been applied: i) trimethylsilylation [26] and ii) esterification with diazomethane [9] or with iii)
93 boron trifluoride in methanol [37].

94 The aim of the present work was the analysis of trace residual contents of five different ceramic samples
95 belonging to five different ceramic jars found in a deposit in Lekeitio (Basque Country, northern Spain)
96 suspected to have been used to store oil from whales from Newfoundland and Labrador captured by
97 Basque whalers in the period from 16th to 17th Century. To fulfil this goal, the archaeological samples as
98 well as the fresh blubber samples used as reference materials were analysed by means of HPLC-ESI-qToF
99 and GC-MS. The former was used to identify TAGs whereas the latter was mainly used to obtain the FA
100 profile as well as to detect new possible biomarkers of whale oil in the archaeological samples.

101 **2. Experimental**

102 2.1. Archaeological samples

103 The archaeological ceramic artifacts under study were collected in a deposit in Lekeitio (Basque Country,
104 northern Spain). Despite no entire ceramic *Amphorae* was found, several fragments without visible
105 residues and corresponding to different ceramic jars (n=5) were analyzed: Lekeitio 002 (L002), Lekeitio
106 003 (L003), Lekeitio 006 (L006), Lekeitio 016 (L016) and Lekeitio 020 (L020) (see Fig. 1).

107 2.2. Fresh blubber and whale oil samples

108 Due to the difficulty to get ancient whale oil samples, four fresh whale blubber samples and a whale oil
109 sample were used as reference materials (see Table 1).

110 Four fresh whale blubber samples belonging to different whale species were provided by the Swedish
111 Museum of Natural History in Stockholm. Three different blubber samples from three different whale
112 species belonging to the sub-order mysticete and genus *Balaenoptera* were characterized: (i) fin whale
113 (*Balaenoptera physalus*), (ii) minke whale (*Balaenoptera acutorostrata*) and (iii) sei whale (*Balaenoptera*
114 *borealis*). The fourth blubber sample was extracted from harbour porpoise specie (*Phocoena phocoena*)
115 belonging to the sub-order odontocete and genus *Phocoena*. The last specie was obtained from whale
116 blubber sampled from a humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*) in Australia belonging to the sub-
117 order mysticete and genus *Megaptera*.

118 Besides the whale blubber samples, a sample of liquid whale oil extracted from fat of unknown whale
119 species in Asturias (Northern Spain) supplied by the Association for the Study and Conservation of
120 Marine Fauna (AMBAR) was characterized.

121 2.3. Reagents and materials

122 Laboratory material was carefully cleaned with abundant pure water ($<0.2 \mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, Millipore, USA) and
123 without using detergent to avoid possible contamination produced by detergent residues. The material
124 was sonicated under clean acetone (Q.P., Panreac Química, Spain) for an hour and then rinsed with
125 ultrapure water ($<0.057 \mu\text{S}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$, Milli-Q model, Millipore, USA). Finally, the glass material was dried in
126 an oven at 400 °C for 4 h.

127 The mix solution of mono and dicarboxylic fatty acids (FAs) in acetone and purchased from Sigma-
128 Aldrich (Milan, Italy) contained lauric acid ($\text{C}_{8:0}$; $0.24 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), suberic acid (C_8 diacid; $0.27 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), azelaic
129 acid (C_9 diacid; $0.28 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), myristic acid ($\text{C}_{14:0}$; $0.25 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), sebacic acid (C_{10} diacid; $0.3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), palmitic
130 acid ($\text{C}_{16:0}$; $0.25 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$), oleic acid ($\text{C}_{18:1}$; $0.51 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and stearic acid ($\text{C}_{18:0}$; $0.51 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) compounds.
131 Tridecanoic acid solution in isooctane ($118.3 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) and hexadecane solution in isooctane ($133.3 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)
132 were both supplied by Sigma–Aldrich (USA) and used as internal standards (ISs).

133 The used solvents n-hexane (Hex), ethyl acetate (EtOAc), methanol (MeOH), ethanol (EtOH), chloroform
134 (CHCl_3), dichloromethane (CH_2Cl_2) and 2-propanol (all HPLC grade, 99.8%) were purchased from LabScan
135 (Dublin, Ireland). Hydrochloric acid (HCl), diethyl ether, potassium hydroxide pellets and N,O-
136 bis(trimethyl)silyltrifluoro-acetamide (BSTFA) containing 1% trimethylchlorosilane, were purchased from
137 Sigma–Aldrich (Milan, Italy).

138 2.4. Sample preparation

139 Special care was taken in all analytical steps (including sample crushing, fractionation and extraction) in
140 order to minimize cross-contamination sources. Ceramic samples (1 g) were collected with a scalpel,
141 both from the external and internal part of the archaeological pieces, weighed and stored in glass
142 vessels until their analysis (see Fig. 1). Fresh whale blubber and oil samples were stored in the supplied
143 glass vials before taking 1-2 mg for analysis.

144 2.5. Sample treatment

145 2.5.1. Solvent soluble fraction: isolation of triacylglycerols (TAGs).

146 Microwave assisted extraction (Milestone microwaves Ethos One, USA) was used to characterize the
147 solvent soluble fraction. The extraction conditions were fixed according to the previous works found in
148 the literature [38,39]. In this work, the extractions were performed at 80°C and 600 W for 25 min using
149 300 µL and 600 µL of a CHCl₃:Hex (3:2, v/v) mixture to extract 1-2 mg of fresh whale oil samples and 1 g
150 of ceramic archaeological samples, respectively. The extracts were completely dried under a nitrogen
151 stream, diluted with 600 µL of MeOH: 2-propanol (90:10, v/v) and filtered through 0.45 µm PTFE filters
152 (Grace Davison Discovery Sciences, U.S.) just before the analysis by HPLC-ESI-QToF.

153 2.5.2. Saponified fraction: isolation of fatty acids (FAs)

154 The extraction of the acidic and neutral compounds was performed according to the methodology
155 described by Colombini et al.[16]. Briefly, 1 g of each archaeological sample was directly subjected to
156 microwave assisted saponification (Milestone microwaves Ethos One, USA) with 600 µL of 10 % KOH in
157 EtOH at 80 °C and 200 W for 60 min. In the case of the fresh samples (i.e., whale blubber and oil
158 samples) used as reference materials 0.5-1 mg were immersed in 300 µL of the previous mentioned
159 saponification solution.

160 After saponification, the alcoholic solutions were diluted in bi-distilled water and the neutral fractions
161 were extracted with Hex (3 x 400 µL). Subsequently, the aqueous phases were acidified with HCl (6 M to
162 pH=2) and re-extracted with diethyl ether (3 x 400 µL). 5 µL of tridecanoic acid solution (118.3 µg·g⁻¹)
163 used as IS was added to the 200 µL of the final EtOAc extract and evaporated to dryness under a gentle
164 stream of nitrogen. Derivatization was performed with 20 µL of BSTFA and 150 µL of isooctane
165 (derivatization solvent) at 60°C for 30 min in a water bath. 5 µL of hexadecane solution (133.3 µg·g⁻¹)
166 used as IS were added to the derivatized extract before the analysis by means of GC-MS.

167 2.6. Instruments and methods

168 2.6.1. High performance liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry

169 HPLC-ESI-Q-ToF analyses were carried out using a 1200 Infinity HPLC, coupled with a Quadrupole-Time
170 of Flight tandem mass spectrometer 6530 Infinity Q-ToF detector by a Jet Stream ESI interface (Agilent

171 Technologies). The chromatographic separation was carried out using a Poroshell 120 EC-C18 column
172 (3.0 mm x 5.0 mm, 2.7 μm particle size) with a Zorbax eclipse plus C-18 guard column (4.6 mm x 12.5
173 mm, 5 mm particle size) at a flow rate of 0.3 mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and 45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Aliquots of 10 μL were injected and the
174 elution gradient was programmed using methanol/water 85:15 (eluent A) and iso-propanol (eluent B) as
175 follows: 90 % A for 5 min, followed by a linear gradient to 90% B in 30 min (held for 10 min). Re-
176 equilibration time for each analysis run was 10 min.

177 The ESI operating conditions were: drying gas (N_2 , purity >98%): 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 10 L $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$; capillary voltage
178 4.5 KV; nebulizer gas 35 psig; sheath gas (N_2 , purity >98%): 375 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 11 L $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. High resolution MS
179 and MS/MS spectra were acquired in positive mode in the range 100-1700 m/z. The fragmentor was
180 kept at 200 V, nozzle voltage 1000 V, skimmer 65 V, octapole RF 750 V. The MS/MS spectra presented
181 in the text were obtained at 50 V. The collision gas was nitrogen (purity 99.999%). The data were
182 collected by auto MS/MS acquisition with an MS scan rate of 1.03 spectra/sec and an MS/MS scan rate
183 of 1.05 spectra/sec; only one precursor was acquired per cycle (relative threshold 0.010%). The mass
184 axis was calibrated daily using the Agilent tuning mix HP0321 (Agilent Technologies). MassHunter[®]
185 Workstation Software (B.04.00) was used to carry out mass spectrometer control, data acquisition and
186 data analysis.

187 The structures of the TAGs were identified with the interpretation of their tandem mass spectra and by
188 comparison with previously published mass spectra data [40-44]. TAGs were named by means of the
189 three abbreviations corresponding to the FAs linked to the glycerol backbone: C, capric acid ($\text{C}_{10:0}$); La,
190 lauric acid ($\text{C}_{12:0}$), M, myristic acid ($\text{C}_{14:0}$); P, palmitic acid ($\text{C}_{16:0}$); Po, palmitoleic acid ($\text{C}_{16:1}$); S, stearic acid
191 ($\text{C}_{18:0}$); O, oleic acid ($\text{C}_{18:1}$); L, linoleic acid ($\text{C}_{18:2}$); Ln, linolenic acid ($\text{C}_{18:3}$); S₄, stearidonic acid ($\text{C}_{18:4}$); E,
192 eicosenoic acid ($\text{C}_{20:1}$); E₂, eicosadienoic acid ($\text{C}_{20:2}$); E₃, eicosatrienoic acid ($\text{C}_{20:3}$); E₄, eicosatetraenoic
193 acid ($\text{C}_{20:4}$); Epa, eicosapentaenoic acid ($\text{C}_{20:5}$); A, arachidic acid ($\text{C}_{20:0}$); D, docosenoic acid ($\text{C}_{22:1}$); Dte,
194 docosatetraenoic acid ($\text{C}_{22:4}$); Dpa, docosapentaenoic acid ($\text{C}_{22:5}$); Dha, docosahexaenoic acid ($\text{C}_{22:6}$); B,
195 behenic acid ($\text{C}_{22:0}$); T, tetracosenoic acid ($\text{C}_{24:1}$).

196 2.6.2. Gas chromatography/mass spectrometry

197 The gas chromatograph system 6890N (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA) was coupled to a 5975
198 mass selective detector (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA) single quadrupole mass spectrometer.
199 2 μL of the derivatized extract were injected in splitless mode at 280 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ into the GC-MS system. For the
200 gas chromatographic separation, a HP-5MS fused silica capillary column (5% diphenyl- 95% dimethyl-
201 polysiloxane, 30 m x 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 μm film thickness, J&W Scientific Agilent Technologies, USA)
202 with a de-activated silica pre-column (2 m x 0.32 mm i.d., J&W Scientific Agilent Technologies, USA) was
203 used. The carrier gas (He, purity 99.9995%) was used in the constant flow mode at 1.2 mL $\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The GC-
204 MS oven program temperature was as follows: 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (2 min), a temperature increase of 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ up to
205 200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (3 min) to continue rising at 10 $^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ up to 280 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (40 min).

206 Measurements were performed in SCAN mode (m/z 50–650) and peak assignments were performed
207 using standard solutions of FAs, mass spectra interpretation, comparison with mass spectral libraries
208 (NIST 2.0) and with published mass spectra [13,16].

209 2.7. Semi-quantitative analysis

210 For the HPLC-ESI-Q-ToF analysis, relative abundances were calculated from extract ion chromatograms,
211 considering the isotopic distribution of the molecular species. To establish the TAG profiles in both
212 archaeological and fresh reference samples the signals were normalized to 100% for each
213 chromatogram.

214 For the GC-MS analysis chromatographic areas of the extract ion chromatograms were calculated and
215 corrected with the signal of n-tridecanoic acid and hexadecane internal standards. The data were
216 normalized to 100% for each chromatogram in both archaeological and fresh materials.

217 3. Results and discussion

218

219 3.1. Characterization of blubber and whale oil reference samples

220 Due to the lack of certified reference material of whale oil, the main characteristic fingerprints of this
221 type of samples were first identified in fresh blubber samples, which were used as reference materials
222 (see section 2.2.).

223 3.1.1. HPLC-ESI-QToF triglycerides profiling

224 HPLC-ESI-Q-TOF was applied for the characterization of the TAG profiles of the reference materials. The
225 identification of each acyl substituent was carried out considering the detected fragment ions and
226 searching for m/z values corresponding to the loss of acyl substituents in position sn-1, sn-2 and sn-3.
227 According to La Nasa et al. [45], several fragmentation studies in the literature show that the losses of
228 acylic chain in position sn-1 and sn-3 are energetically more favoured than the loss in the sn-2 position
229 in the case of sodiated adducts. Consequently, it is expected that diacylglycerol ions of sn-1 and sn-3
230 position fragments in the MS-MS spectra will be the more abundant ones [45,46]. Fig. 2 shows the mass
231 spectrum of PPOp in which the previous theory is also shown: the relative abundances of both the
232 sodiated and proton adducts resulting from the losses in position sn-1 ($[PoO]^+$ and $[PoO+Na]^+$) and sn-3
233 ($[PPo]^+$ and $[PPo+Na]^+$) are higher than the corresponding ones for the adducts $[PO]^+$ and $[PO+Na]^+$ that
234 result from the loss of the acyl group in the sn-2 position. However, this interpretation is not always
235 useful for the identification of those complex oils with TAGs containing high amounts of omega-3 long
236 chain polyunsaturated FAs (PUFAs). In this latter case, the differentiation between collisionally-induced
237 and thermally-induced ions could be the key to end-up with their identification. Baiocchi et al. [41]
238 observed an inversion of abundance profiles when comparing thermal- and collision- induced
239 fragmentations for this kind of TAGs when studying samples of tuna oil. In this latter case, the most
240 abundant peaks are due to fragment ions corresponded to the loss of fatty acid from the sn-2 position.

241 Consequently, in the present work the first mentioned fragmentation pattern was used for those
242 saturated or modestly unsaturated FAs whereas for those TAGs containing omega-3 PUFA the
243 collisionally-induced fragmentation observed in the literature was taken into account.

244 Table 2 shows the 91 TAGs identified in fresh blubber and whale oil samples used as reference
245 materials. Their relative abundance was obtained based on their MS peak area. As it can be seen most of
246 them are characterized by the presence of the two main omega-3 long PUFAs: acyl chains
247 docosahexaenoic acid and eicosapentaenoic acid.

248 Some of the most abundant TAGs in all the characterized whale blubber samples are Epa-O-P, Dha-P-O,
249 Epa-O-O, Dha-P-O, P-Po-Epa and E-O-O, A-O-O. In concordance with other works studying TAGs in other
250 marine species, the omega-3 FAs Dha and Epa were on the backbones of the TAGs with higher level of
251 monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFAs) such as palmitoleic (Po), oleic (O), eicosenoic (E) and docosenoic
252 (D) acids than saturated FAs [43]. Auto MS-MS acquisition mode in HPLC-ESI-QToF allows the non-target
253 screening of as many as possible TAGs in the sample except for those cases in which chromatographic
254 coelution of compounds with the same parent ion occur. Exemplarily, this happens for the precursor ion
255 991.8 (Fig. 3) which, according to the product ions, can correspond to E-D-O (ions 709.6 for [ED+Na]⁺
256 and 681.5 for [DO+Na]⁺) or D-Po-D (ions 653.5 for [PoD+Na]⁺). Due to the homogeneity of their structure
257 and the absence of PUFAs, the fragmentation behaviour for both TAGs is explained by the energetically
258 more favoured losses in positions sn-1 and sn-3. As it can be seen, the major composition corresponds
259 to E-D-O due to the higher abundance of the product 709.6 ([ED+Na]⁺) with respect to the 653.5
260 ([PoD+Na]⁺ or [EO+Na]⁺). Nevertheless, the occurrence of the product with m/z 737.6 ([DD+Na]⁺)
261 confirms the presence of D-Po-D.

262 The obtained TAG profiles in fresh material were compared among the different whale species in order
263 to study possible similarities that could be used as markers. According to the results shown in Fig. 4, it
264 can be clearly observed that there is a close TAG distribution profile for all the blubber samples
265 belonging to Balaenoptera genus (i.e., sei whale, fin whale and minke whale) whereas totally different
266 distributions were found for the rest of the studied genus (i.e., Phocoena and Megaptera). Thus, it can
267 be suggested that the TAG profile could be related to the genus of the whale from which oil or blubber
268 has been extracted. Due to the faster degradation of the polyunsaturated TAGs with respect to the
269 saturated or modestly unsaturated ones, it is highly unlikely to find them preserved in the
270 archaeological ceramic samples. Nevertheless, the TAGs marked in bold in Table 2 were found in real
271 archaeological samples (see below), thus, they were considered in order to study trends and ratios in
272 the fresh material.

273 Fig. 5 shows the tendencies of the previously mentioned TAGs in the reference blubber samples and as
274 it can be observed, even taking only into account the modestly unsaturated TAGs, five common
275 distributions can be observed for samples belonging to the same whale genus, this is, similar tendencies
276 for the TAGs (highlighted in boxes, Fig. 5) of the species belonging to Balaenoptera genus whereas they

277 remain different or not constant in the case of Phocoena and Megaptera. Additionally, these
278 distributions gave us a clue about the possible genus of the whale from which blubber was extracted
279 and transformed into oil since the unknown whale oil sample follows the same pattern as the samples
280 from Balaenoptera genus.

281 Taking into account that the tendencies of the groups of TAGs (highlighted in boxes, Fig. 5) remain
282 constant, some ratios were calculated in order to verify that those calculated for the species belonging
283 to Balaenoptera genus were different from the ones corresponding to Phocoena and Megaptera.
284 Nevertheless, those groups involving TAGs with a higher number of total unsaturations (i.e. groups 4
285 and 5 in Fig. 5) were not taken into account in order to establish the ratios due to their different
286 degradation rate with time. Thus, four ratios were defined and calculated for the blubber samples:
287 LaPO/LaPL, PPoO/POP, MOP/SPoM and MOLa/MLaL. As it can be seen in Table 3, there are no statistical
288 differences among the four ratios of TAGs for sei, fin and minke whales from Balaenoptera genus,
289 whereas statistically different results were found for humpback whale (Phocoena genus) and harbour
290 porpoise (Megaptera genus) whales. The ratios calculated with the TAGs found in the unknown whale
291 oil match those obtained for Balaenoptera species.

292 3.1.2. GC-MS fatty acid analysis

293 In order to obtain complementary information on the composition of the reference materials, GC-MS
294 analysis after saponification, extraction and derivatization was applied to the fresh blubber samples. As
295 expected, the identified FAs in the blubber and whale oil were in agreement with the lipid profile
296 identified by HPLC-MS analysis. In this way, all the PUFAs, MUFAs and saturated FAs that form the TAGs
297 in Table 2 were found in all the blubber and whale oil samples being oleic (C_{18:1}), palmitoleic (C_{16:1}),
298 palmitic (C_{16:0}), miristic (C_{14:0}), gondoic (C_{20:1}) and cetoleic (C_{22:1}) acids the most abundant ones, which is
299 in agreement with literature [47-52].

300 Similarly to the results obtained by HPLC analyses, the distributions of the FAs in the different reference
301 materials were compared and very similar trends were found for all the studied whale samples (data not
302 shown).

303 Some ratios of FAs were also calculated and palmitic to palmitoleic ratio showed different response
304 according to the genus of the analyzed whale oil. In fact, higher concentrations of palmitic acid were
305 found in all the species of Balaenoptera genus whereas palmitoleic acid was found at higher
306 concentrations in the rest of studied whales from different genus (i.e., Phocoena and Megaptera) as the
307 main FA. These results are in concordance with the obtained results by means of HPLC-ESI-Q-ToF when
308 having a look at the calculated ratios for the TAGs in Table 3. The ratio PPoO/POP, which indicates the
309 relation between palmitoleic and palmitic, is significantly higher in the case of the whales of genus
310 Megaptera and Phocoena (3.02 and 2.15, respectively) whereas for Balaenoptera is lower (<1.23), as it
311 was previously concluded from GC-MS analysis. This phenomenon is also observed using the MOP/SPoM

312 ratio that involves the inverse situation (i.e., palmitic to palmitoleic acid). In the later, values lower than
313 1 are obtained for Megaptera and Phocoena (0.98 and 0.54 respectively) and values higher than 1 for
314 Balaenoptera (>1.24). The whale oil from unknown origin also matches Balaenoptera genus according to
315 the GC-MS analysis. Consequently, the combination of GC-MS and HPLC-ESI-Q-ToF could be an adequate
316 approach to distinguish the genus of the blubber under study.

317 According to the literature, in addition to the already mentioned FAs, other biomarkers that enable the
318 marine lipid identification must be detected to meet the criteria established by Evershed et al. [53].
319 These compounds are isoprenoid acids, particularly 4,8,12-trimethyltridecanoic acid (4,8,12-TMTD),
320 2,6,10,14-tetramethylpentadecanoic acid (pristanic acid) and 3,7,11,25-tetramethylhexadecanoic acid
321 (phytanic acid), which are found at high abundance in aquatic oils and marine tissues (specially whale
322 oils) but are absent in plants, since they originate from ingested phytoplankton [54]. The three
323 isoprenoid FAs were detected in all the fresh blubber samples.

324 3.2. Characterization of organic residues from archaeological ceramic samples

325 3.2.1. TAGs

326 The archaeological ceramics followed the same treatment as the fresh samples used as reference
327 material in order to determine the content in TAGs. As it has been previously mentioned, no PUFAs
328 were found in the chains of the identified TAGs due to their higher susceptibility to degrade with time.
329 Nevertheless, all the modestly unsaturated TAGs found in fresh materials shown in Fig. 5 were found in
330 the ancient material. Fig. 6 shows the distributions of the TAGs found in archaeological samples and in
331 general terms they match with the TAG profiles (highlighted in boxes) observed for the whales of
332 Balaenoptera genus (i.e., sei, fin and minke whales). However, there are some TAGs in the
333 archaeological samples that show a decrease with respect to the fresh material as it is the case of Po-O-
334 L/L-L-P and O-Ln-O/LLO TAGs (marked with an asterisk in boxes 4 and 5 in Fig. 6). This decay could be
335 attributed to the larger number of unsaturations present in Po-O-L/L-L-P (4 unsaturations) and O-Ln-
336 O/LLO (5 unsaturations) in comparison to the rest of TAGs (<4 unsaturations).

337 As a matter of fact, the compounds with the highest degree of unsaturations (Ln-Ln-Ln and L-L-L/Ln-L-O
338 with 9 and 6 unsaturations, respectively) (see Fig. 5) were not identified in the archaeological ceramics.
339 In addition, not only the total number of unsaturations influences the degradation of the TAGs but also
340 the unsaturation degree of each acyl chain that forms the TAG. The oxidation rate depends significantly
341 on the number of unsaturations per chain, increasing over ten times for each double bond present
342 [3,55]. According to DeMan et al. [56], the oxidation rate of stearic acid compared to oleic (O), linoleic
343 acid (L) and linolenic acid at 100°C is 1:100:1200:2500, but the precise relative rate at which this type of
344 fats are decomposed depends on the temperature, oxygen and water availability. In any case, both
345 linoleic and linolenic acids are often found at lower concentrations in comparison to the rest of FAs due
346 to their faster degradation rate [56], a fact that is also found in the present work.

347 Finally, as it can be seen in Table 3, there are no statistical differences between the ratios of LaPO/LaPL,
348 PPO/POP, MOP/SPoM and MOLa/MLaL for the blubber of Balaenoptera (sei, fin and minke whales) and
349 the ones calculated for the archaeological materials. Thus, these ratios can be applied in the future both
350 to fresh and archaeological materials in order to establish the source or the possible genus of whale
351 from which oil and blubber have been extracted.

352 3.2.2. FAs and degradation products

353 The organic residues preserved in all the archaeological ceramic samples were mainly saturated FAs
354 such as, lauric (C_{12:0}), myristic (C_{14:0}), palmitic (C_{16:0}), stearic (C_{18:0}), arachidic (C_{20:0}) and behenic (C_{22:0})
355 acids together with several MUFAs (oleic (C_{18:1}), palmitoleic (C_{16:1}), gondoic (C_{20:1}), cetoleic (C_{22:1}) and
356 nervonic (C_{24:1}) acids). Diunsaturated FAs (linoleic (C_{18:2}) and eicosadienoic acid (C_{20:2})) were only
357 identified in sample L016 (see Fig. 7).

358 Additionally, degradation of FAs during the burial period led to the appearance of several organic
359 products that have been used in literature as lipid biomarkers. For example, the oxidative cleavage of
360 PUFAs can form dicarboxylic acids (diacids) [24,57]. Different mechanisms lead to the formation of these
361 diacids being the oxidation of any FA with a double bond in position 9 (e.g. oleic acid) the most common
362 transformation, generating azelaic acid (C₉ diacid) which has been detected in samples L003, L006, L016
363 and L020. Azelaic acid or pimelic acid (C₇ diacid found in L003, L016 and L020) can be formed from
364 PUFAs, such as linoleic and linolenic acids or oleic and palmitoleic acids, respectively [13,15]. On the
365 other hand, succinic acid (C₄ diacid) and glutaric acid (C₅ diacid), found in sample L016, can be formed
366 from Epa and Dha, respectively [58]. Long-chain MUFAs such as gondoic and cetoleic acids (found in all
367 the archaeological ceramic samples) with double bonds at position 11 are the primary source for diacids
368 with more than 9 carbons such as undecanedioic acid [15], which was also found in all the
369 archaeological samples (see Fig. 7).

370 In addition to the already mentioned degradation products, dihydroxy fatty acids were also detected at
371 high abundance levels, especially in sample L016. These compounds are known to have the hydroxyl
372 groups in the position of the double bond in the precursor Z-monounsaturated fatty acids (C_{14:0})
373 [1,23,59]. Dihydroxy fatty acids are recognized biomarkers for detecting processed marine animal
374 products [23,60]. Besides, these compounds are only released from the potsherds by strong alkaline
375 treatment due to the ester linkages that they form with the matrix [23]. In all the ceramic samples
376 (except in sample L006), several dihydroxy fatty acids such as 9,10-dihydroxyhexadecanoic acid, 9,10-
377 dihydroxyoctadecanoic acid, 9,10-dihydroxyeicosanoic acid, 11,12-dihydroxyeicosanoic acid and 11,12-
378 dihydroxydocosanoic acid were detected (see Fig. 7). They derived from the precursors palmitoleic,
379 oleic, gadoleic, gondoic and cetoleic acids, respectively. Concretely, the high abundance of 11,12-
380 dihydroxydocosanoic acid (coming from cetoleic acid) in the archaeological samples provides the
381 evidence to support the marine origin of the lipid residues preserved in the studied samples [13].

382 The profile of the FAs found in both the fresh reference blubber samples and the archaeological
383 ceramics was compared to study possible similarities. The FAs profile found for archaeological samples
384 were comparable to those found for sei whale, fin whale and minke whale, all belonging to
385 Balaenoptera genus (see Fig. 8a). In fact, all the detected compounds followed the same trend in all the
386 analyzed samples except the unsaturated FAs (i.e., palmitoleic, oleic, gondoic and cetoleic acids), which
387 showed decay due to the ageing of the samples. This assumption is evidenced by the appearance of
388 degradation products such as pimelic, azelaic, sebacic and undecanedioic acid. Nevertheless, the
389 comparison of samples' profile to the ones obtained for Phocoena and Megaptera fresh blubber
390 samples (see Fig. 8.b) showed a pronounced difference for palmitoleic acid as well as for palmitic and
391 stearic acids.

392 3.2.3. Isoprenoid compounds and sterols

393 The isoprenoid biomarkers 4,8,12-TMTD, pristanic acid and phytanic acid were all detected in all the
394 archaeological ceramic samples except in the case of sample L002. In this way, the marine lipid
395 identification (see Fig. 7) was accomplished using the already mentioned criteria (see section 3.1.2.).

396 Cholesterol, which is the main biomarker of animal fats, was also detected in the neutral fraction of four
397 of the five samples (L002, L003, L006, and L016). Cholesterol and squalene were found in all the blubber
398 samples and, due to the higher stability with time of the former, it can survive in the walls of the
399 archaeological ceramics, whereas squalene was not found since it rapidly degrades and can be the result
400 of handling contamination [13].

401 Pristane is another isoprenoid that was detected for the first time in the neutral fraction of both fresh
402 and archaeological samples. Blumer et al. isolated pristane in high concentrations from the copepod
403 *Calanus finmarchicus*, small crustaceans found in the sea, and after subsequent analysis on a large
404 variety of marine organisms it appeared likely that *Calanus* was the main source of pristane for marine
405 predators such as sharks or whales [61]. Blumer pinpointed that phytol can be converted into pristane
406 by these copepods and this way it becomes part of the marine lipid pool [61,62]. Additionally, pristane is
407 a specific product of organisms of limited geographical occurrence and large populations of *Calanus*
408 *finmarchicus* are present in the coasts of Labrador and Newfoundland due to the large amount of
409 phytoplankton accumulated in these regions [63]. Thus, it can be hypothesized that pristane coming
410 from these crustaceans can be accumulated in the fat of the whales and survive in the walls of the
411 ceramic containers due to their high stability.

412 4. Conclusions

413 To our knowledge this is the first time that HPLC-ESI-Q-ToF is applied to the analysis of whale blubber
414 and oil to characterize the structure of the TAGs. Despite not being able to know the exact position of
415 each acyl chain in those cases in which PUFAs were present since there was no possibility to perform
416 MS³ experiments, the obtained results allowed us to distinguish among whales of different genus just by

417 looking at their TAG profiles. In fact, it has been possible to identify the most likely genus (Balaenoptera)
418 of the unknown whale from which oil was extracted. These results could be complemented in future
419 works by MSⁿ or even ¹³C-NMR analyses to study the regioisomeric distribution of the FAs forming the
420 complex TAGs in whale oil.

421 On the other hand, this work presents also the determination of the TAG profile of organic residues
422 preserved in archaeological ceramic samples. The use of TAG distributions as well as specific TAG ratios
423 (i.e., PPoO/POP and MOP/SPoM) can provide the clues to identify the genus of the analyzed organic
424 residue. In this work, the distributions and ratios of these TAGs agree with those found for the fresh
425 blubber samples of the whale species of Balaenoptera genus (fin whale, sei whale and minke whale)
426 used as reference materials; thus, it can be suggested the possible genus of some of the whales that
427 Basque whalers used to capture. Of course, this analysis should be extrapolated to a higher number of
428 samples of blubber from different species (of different genus) as well as to other archaeological ceramic
429 samples, since the range of whales that Basque people used to hunt is higher. McLeod et al. analyzed
430 whale bones from several Basque whaling stations in the Strait of Belle Isle and Gulf of St. Lawrence by
431 extracting their DNA and they only identified a single right whale (genus Eubalaena) bone and 203
432 bowhead whale (genus Balaena) bones from at least 72 individuals [64]. Thus, blubber samples from
433 these species should be analyzed in subsequent experiments following the methodologies described in
434 this work in order to study differences and similarities with species from Balaenoptera genus.

435 The application of GC-MS analysis to both fresh and archaeological materials confirmed the obtained
436 information by HPLC-ESI-Q-ToF using the profiles of the detected FAs. Additionally, the identified
437 isoprenoid biomarkers (pristanic, phytanic and 4,8,12-TMTD acids) together with the degradation
438 products (dicarboxylic fatty acids and dihydroxy fatty acids) meet the established criteria for the
439 confirmation of the presence of marine lipids in ceramic vessels. Finally, pristane has been suggested as
440 a possible new marine biomarker due to its presence in fresh material and its high stability in
441 archaeological ceramics.

442 The obtained data in this work confirm the use of the large ceramic jars found in Lekeitio as whale oil
443 containers and highlights the importance of applying different methodologies to obtain as much
444 information as possible by the search of already known biomarkers as well as new ones.

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636 **LIST OF TABLES**

637 **Table 1.** Description of the whale blubbers and oil used as reference materials.

638 **Table 2.** Triglycerides (TAGs) determined by HPLC-ESI-Q-ToF in the reference whale blubbers
639 and oil with formula, parent ions, daughter ions and proposed fragmentation of the
640 mass spectra and tandem mass spectra for all the identified species

641 **Table 3.** TAG ratios calculated for the reference materials and the archaeological samples.

Table 1: description of the whale blubbers and oil used as reference materials.

Sample type	Whale sub-order	Genus	Specie	Source
Whale Blubber	Mysticete	Balaenoptera	Fin Whale (<i>Balaenoptera physalus</i>)	Swedish Museum of Natural History in Stockholm
			Minke Whale (<i>Balaenoptera acutorostrata</i>)	
			Sei Whale (<i>Balaenoptera borealis</i>)	
		Megaptera	Humpback Whale (<i>Megaptera novaeangliae</i>)	Australia
	Odontocete	Phocoena	Harbour Porpoise (<i>Phocoena phocoena</i>)	Swedish Museum of Natural History in Stockholm
Whale Oil	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Association for the Study and Conservation of Marine Fauna (AMBAR)

644 Table 2: Triglycerides (TAGs) determined by HPLC-ESI-Q-ToF in the reference whale blubbers and oil with formula,
 645 parent ions, daughter ions and proposed fragmentation of the mass spectra and tandem mass spectra for all the
 646 identified species

TAG structure	MS ¹		MS ²					
	Formula	Precursor ion [M+Na] ⁺	Major fragments			Minor fragments		
			Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern
M-P-La	C ₄₅ H ₈₆ O ₆	745.6	545.4	[MP+Na] ⁺	517.4	[PLa+Na] ⁺	489.4	[MLa+Na] ⁺
			523.4	[MP] ⁺	495.4	[PLa] ⁺	467.4	[MLa] ⁺
M-La-L	C ₄₇ H ₈₆ O ₆	769.6	541.4	[LaL+Na] ⁺	489.4	[MLa+Na] ⁺	569.5	[ML+Na] ⁺
			519.4	[LaL] ⁺	467.4	[MLa] ⁺	547.5	[ML] ⁺
M-O-La	C ₄₇ H ₈₈ O ₆	771.6	571.4	[MO+Na] ⁺	543.4	[OLa+Na] ⁺	489.4	[MLa+Na] ⁺
			549.4	[MO] ⁺	521.4	[OLa] ⁺	467.4	[MLa] ⁺
La-P-L	C ₄₉ H ₉₀ O ₆	797.6	517.4	[LaP+Na] ⁺	597.5	[PL+Na] ⁺	541.4	[LaL+Na] ⁺
			495.4	[LaP] ⁺	575.5	[PL] ⁺	519.4	[LaL] ⁺
O-C-O	C ₄₉ H ₉₀ O ₆	797.6	515.4	[OC+Na] ⁺			625.5	[OO+Na] ⁺
			493.4	[OC] ⁺			603.5	[OO] ⁺
O-La-P	C ₄₉ H ₉₂ O ₆	799.6	543.4	[OLa+Na] ⁺	517.4	[LaP+Na] ⁺	599.5	[OP+Na] ⁺
			521.4	[OLa] ⁺	495.4	[LaP] ⁺	577.5	[OP] ⁺
M-P-P	C ₄₉ H ₉₄ O ₆	801.7	545.4	[MP+Na] ⁺	573.5	[PP+Na] ⁺		
			523.4	[MP] ⁺	551.5	[PP] ⁺		
Po-O-M	C ₅₁ H ₉₆ O ₆	825.7	597.5	[PoO+Na] ⁺	571.5	[MO+Na] ⁺	543.4	[PoM+Na] ⁺
			575.5	[PoO] ⁺	549.5	[MO] ⁺	521.4	[PoM] ⁺
M-O-P	C ₅₁ H ₉₆ O ₆	827.7	571.5	[MO+Na] ⁺	599.5	[OP+Na] ⁺	545.4	[MP+Na] ⁺
			549.5	[MO] ⁺	577.5	[OP] ⁺	523.4	[MP] ⁺
P-P-P	C ₅₁ H ₉₈ O ₆	829.7	573.5	[PP+Na] ⁺	551.5	[PP] ⁺		
M-Po-Epa	C ₅₅ H ₉₀ O ₆	845.6	543.4	[MPo+Na] ⁺	569.4	[MEpa] ⁺		
			521.4	[MPO] ⁺	617.4	[PoEPA+Na] ⁺		
			591.4	[MEpa+Na] ⁺	595.4	[PoEPA] ⁺		
M-O-Ln	C ₅₃ H ₉₄ O ₆	849.7	571.5	[MO+Na] ⁺	621.5	[OLn+Na] ⁺		
			549.5	[MO] ⁺	599.5	[OLn] ⁺		
			567.5	[MLn+Na] ⁺	545.5	[MLn] ⁺		
P-Po-Ln	C ₅₃ H ₉₄ O ₆	849.7	571.5	[PPo+Na] ⁺	571.5	[PoLn] ⁺		
			549.5	[PPo] ⁺	595.7	[LnP+Na] ⁺		
			593.5	[PoLn+Na] ⁺	573.5	[LnP] ⁺		
M-L-L	C ₅₃ H ₉₄ O ₆	849.7	569.5	[ML+Na] ⁺	621.5	[LL+Na] ⁺		
			547.5	[ML] ⁺	599.5	[LL] ⁺		
Ln-P-P	C ₅₃ H ₉₆ O ₆	851.7	595.7	[LnP+Na] ⁺	573.5	[PP+Na] ⁺		
			573.5	[LnP] ⁺	551.5	[PP] ⁺		
P-Po-O	C ₅₃ H ₉₈ O ₆	853.7	571.5	[PPo+Na] ⁺	597.5	[PoO+Na] ⁺	599.5	[PO+Na] ⁺
			549.5	[PPo] ⁺	575.5	[PoO] ⁺	577.5	[PO] ⁺
P-O-P	C ₅₃ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	855.7	599.5	[PO+Na] ⁺	577.5	[PO] ⁺		
P-P-O	C ₅₃ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	855.7	573.5	[PP+Na] ⁺	599.5	[PO+Na] ⁺		
			551.5	[PP] ⁺	577.5	[PO] ⁺		

Table 2: continuation

MS ¹			MS ²					
TAG structure	Formula	Precursor ion [M+Na] ⁺	Major fragments				Minor fragments	
			Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern
P-P-S	C ₅₃ H ₁₀₂ O ₆	857.7	573.5 551.5	[PP+Na] ⁺ [PP] ⁺	601.5 579.5	[PS+Na] ⁺ [PS] ⁺		
P-Po-Epa	C ₅₅ H ₉₄ O ₆	873.7	571.5 549.5 619.5	[PPo+Na] ⁺ [PPo] ⁺ [PEpa+Na] ⁺	597.5 617.4 595.4	[PEpa] ⁺ [PoEPA+Na] ⁺ [PoEPA] ⁺		
P-O-Ln	C ₅₅ H ₉₈ O ₆	877.7	599.5 577.5 621.5	[PO+Na] ⁺ [PO] ⁺ [OLn+Na] ⁺	599.5 595.7 573.5	[OLn] ⁺ [PLn+Na] ⁺ [PLn] ⁺		
Po-O-L	C ₅₅ H ₉₈ O ₆	877.7	597.5 575.5	[PoO+Na] ⁺ [PoO] ⁺	623.5 601.5	[OL+Na] ⁺ [OL] ⁺	595.5 573.5	[PoL+Na] ⁺ [PoL] ⁺
PLL	C ₅₅ H ₉₈ O ₆	877.7	597.5 575.5	[PL+Na] ⁺ [PL] ⁺	621.5 599.5	[LL+Na] ⁺ [LL] ⁺		
Po-O-O	C ₅₅ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	879.7	597.5 575.5	[PoO+Na] ⁺ [PoO] ⁺	625.5 603.5	[OO+Na] ⁺ [OO] ⁺		
O-P-O	C ₅₅ H ₁₀₂ O ₆	881.7	599.5	[OP+Na] ⁺	577.5	[OP] ⁺		
P-O-O	C ₅₅ H ₁₀₂ O ₆	881.7	599.5 577.5	[PO+Na] ⁺ [PO] ⁺	625.5 603.5	[OO+Na] ⁺ [OO] ⁺		
P-O-S	C ₅₅ H ₁₀₄ O ₆	883.7	599.5 577.5	[PO+Na] ⁺ [PO] ⁺	627.5 605.5	[OS+Na] ⁺ [OS] ⁺	601.5 579.5	[SP+Na] ⁺ [SP] ⁺
P-S-S	C ₅₅ H ₁₀₆ O ₆	885.7	601.5 579.5	[PS+Na] ⁺ [PS] ⁺	629.5 607.5	[SS+Na] ⁺ [SS] ⁺		
Ln-Ln-Ln	C ₅₇ H ₉₂ O ₆	895.7	617.5	[LnLn+Na] ⁺	595.5	[LnLn] ⁺		
Epa-O-Po	C ₅₉ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	899.7	617.5 645.5	[EpaPo+Na] ⁺ [OEpa+Na] ⁺	597.5 575.5	[PoO+Na] ⁺ [PoO] ⁺	595.5 623.5	[EpaPo] ⁺ [OEpa] ⁺
Epa-O-P	C ₅₇ H ₉₈ O ₆	901.7	645.5 619.5	[OEpa+Na] ⁺ [EpaP+Na] ⁺	599.5 577.5	[PO+Na] ⁺ [PO] ⁺	623.5	[OEpa] ⁺
L-L-L	C ₅₇ H ₉₈ O ₆	901.7	621.5	[LL+Na] ⁺	599.5	[LL] ⁺		
Ln-L-O	C ₅₇ H ₉₈ O ₆	901.7	619.5 597.5 621.5	[LnL+Na] ⁺ [LnL] ⁺ [OLn+Na] ⁺	623.5 601.5 599.5	[LO+Na] ⁺ [LO] ⁺ [OLn] ⁺		
P-O-E ₄	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	903.7	599.5 577.5	[PO+Na] ⁺ [PO] ⁺	621.5 647.5	[PE ₄ +Na] ⁺ [OE ₄ +Na] ⁺	625.5 625.5	[OE ₄] ⁺ [OO+Na] ⁺
O-Ln-O	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	903.7	621.5 599.5	[OLn+Na] ⁺ [OLn] ⁺	625.5 603.5	[OO+Na] ⁺ [OO] ⁺	603.5	[OO] ⁺
L-L-O	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	903.7	621.5 599.5	[LL+Na] ⁺ [LL] ⁺	623.5 601.5	[LO+Na] ⁺ [LO] ⁺		
O-O-L	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₂ O ₆	905.7	625.5 603.5	[OO+Na] ⁺ [OO] ⁺	623.5 601.5	[LO+Na] ⁺ [LO] ⁺		
O-L-O	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₂ O ₆	905.7	623.5	[LO+Na] ⁺	601.5	[LO] ⁺	625.5	[OO+Na] ⁺

Table 2: continuation

MS ¹			MS ²					
TAG structure	Formula	Precursor ion [M+Na] ⁺	Major fragments				Minor fragments	
			Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern
			601.5	[LO] ⁺			603.5	[OO] ⁺
S-O-Ln	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₂ O ₆	905.7	627.5	[SO+Na] ⁺	621.5	[OLn+Na] ⁺		
			605.5	[SO] ⁺	599.5	[OLn] ⁺		
			623.5	[SLn+Na] ⁺	601.5	[SLn] ⁺		
O-O-O	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₄ O ₆	907.7	625.5	[OO+Na] ⁺	603.5	[OO] ⁺		
S-L-O	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₄ O ₆	907.7	625.5	[SL+Na] ⁺	623.5	[LO+Na] ⁺	627.5	[SO+Na] ⁺
			603.5	[SL] ⁺	601.5	[LO] ⁺	605.5	[SO] ⁺
O-O-S	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₆ O ₆	909.7	625.5	[OO+Na] ⁺	627.5	[OS+Na] ⁺		
			603.5	[OO] ⁺	605.5	[OS] ⁺		
E-P-O	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₆ O ₆	909.8	627.5	[EP+Na] ⁺	599.5	[PO+Na] ⁺	653.5	[EO+Na] ⁺
			605.5	[EP] ⁺	577.5	[PO] ⁺	631.5	[EO] ⁺
S-S-O	C ₅₇ H ₁₀₈ O ₆	911.8	629.5	[SS+Na] ⁺	627.5	[SO+Na] ⁺		
			607.5	[SS] ⁺	605.5	[SO] ⁺		
Po-Epa-Epa	C ₅₉ H ₉₂ O ₆	919.6	617.5	[PoEpa+Na] ⁺	643.5	[EpaEpa] ⁺	595.5	[EpaPo] ⁺
			665.5	[EpaEpa+Na] ⁺				
M-Epa-Dha	C ₅₉ H ₉₂ O ₆	919.6	591.5	[MEpa+Na] ⁺	691.5	[DhaEpa] ⁺	569.5	[MEpa] ⁺
			617.5	[DhaM+Na] ⁺			595.5	[DhaM] ⁺
Dha-O-Po	C ₅₉ H ₉₈ O ₆	925.7	643.5	[DhaPo+Na] ⁺	575.5	[OPo] ⁺	649.5	[DhaO] ⁺
			597.5	[OPo+Na] ⁺	671.5	[DhaO+Na] ⁺	621.5	[DhaPo] ⁺
Epa-O-O	C ₅₉ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	927.7	645.5	[EpaO+Na] ⁺	603.5	[OO] ⁺	623.5	[EpaO] ⁺
			625.5	[OO+Na] ⁺				
Dha-P-O	C ₅₉ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	927.7	645.5	[DhaP+Na] ⁺	577.5	[PO] ⁺		
			599.5	[PO+Na] ⁺	671.5	[DhaO+Na] ⁺		
Dpa-O-P	C ₅₉ H ₁₀₂ O ₆	929.7	647.5	[DpaP+Na] ⁺	599.5	[OP+Na] ⁺		
			673.5	[DpaO+Na] ⁺	577.5	[OP] ⁺		
E ₄ -O-S	C ₅₉ H ₁₀₄ O ₆	931.7	649.5	[E ₄ S+Na] ⁺	605.5	[OS] ⁺		
			627.5	[OS+Na] ⁺				
Dte-O-P	C ₅₉ H ₁₀₄ O ₆	931.7	675.5	[DteO+Na] ⁺	653.5	[DteO] ⁺		
			599.5	[OP+Na] ⁺	577.5	[OP] ⁺		
			649.5	[DteP+Na] ⁺	627.5	[DteP] ⁺		
L-E₂-O	C ₅₉ H ₁₀₄ O ₆	931.7	651.5	[E ₂ O+Na] ⁺	649.5	[LE ₂ +Na] ⁺	623.5	[LO+Na] ⁺
			629.5	[E ₂ O] ⁺	627.5	[LE ₂] ⁺	601.5	[LO] ⁺
E-L-O	C ₅₉ H ₁₀₆ O ₆	933.7	651.5	[EL+Na] ⁺	623.5	[LO+Na] ⁺	653.5	[EO+Na] ⁺
			629.5	[EL] ⁺	601.5	[LO] ⁺	631.5	[EO] ⁺
E-O-O	C ₅₉ H ₁₀₈ O ₆	935.8	653.5	[EO+Na] ⁺	625.5	[OO+Na] ⁺		
			631.5	[EO] ⁺	603.5	[OO] ⁺		
A-O-O	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ O ₆	937.8	655.5	[AO+Na] ⁺	625.5	[OO+Na] ⁺		
			633.5	[AO] ⁺	603.5	[OO] ⁺		
Dha-Dha-Mo	C ₆₁ H ₉₂ O ₆	943.7	717.5	[DhaDha+Na] ⁺	615.4	[DhaMo+Na] ⁺	695.5	[DhaDha] ⁺
			615.4	[DhaMo+Na] ⁺			593.5	[DhaMo] ⁺

Table 2: continuation

MS ¹			MS ²					
TAG structure	Formula	Precursor ion [M+Na] ⁺	Major fragments				Minor fragments	
			Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern
Po-Epa-Dha	C ₆₁ H ₉₄ O ₆	945.7	617.5 643.5	[PoEpa+Na] ⁺ [DhaPo+Na] ⁺	691.5	[DhaEpa+Na] ⁺	595.5 621.5	[PoEpa] ⁺ [DhaPo] ⁺
Dha-Dha-M	C ₆₁ H ₉₄ O ₆	945.7	617.5 717.5	[DhaM+Na] ⁺ [DhaDha+Na] ⁺			595.5 695.5	[DhaM] ⁺ [DhaDha] ⁺
Dha-S ₄ -O	C ₆₁ H ₉₆ O ₆	947.7	619.5 665.5	[DhaS ₄ +Na] ⁺ [S ₄ O+Na] ⁺	671.5	[DhaO+Na] ⁺	597.5 643.5	[DhaS ₄] ⁺ [S ₄ O] ⁺
Dha-Dpa-M	C ₆₁ H ₉₆ O ₆	947.7	619.5 617.5	[DpaM+Na] ⁺ [DhaM+Na] ⁺	719.5	[DhaDpa+Na] ⁺	597.5 595.5	[DpaM] ⁺ [DhaM] ⁺
P-E ₄ -Dha	C ₆₁ H ₉₈ O ₆	949.7	621.5 645.5	[PE ₄ +Na] ⁺ [PDha+Na] ⁺	693.5	[A4Dha+Na] ⁺	671.5 599.5	[E ₄ Dha] ⁺ [PE ₄] ⁺
P-E ₃ -Dha	C ₆₁ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	951.7	623.5 695.5	[PE ₃ +Na] ⁺ [E ₃ Dha+Na] ⁺	645.5	[PDha+Na] ⁺	601.5 673.5	[PE ₃] ⁺ [E ₃ Dha] ⁺
Dha-O-O	C ₆₁ H ₁₀₂ O ₆	953.7	671.5 625.5	[DhaO+Na] ⁺ [OO+Na] ⁺	603.5	[OO] ⁺	649.5	[DhaO] ⁺
Dha-S-O	C ₆₁ H ₁₀₄ O ₆	955.7	673.5 627.5	[DhaS+Na] ⁺ [SO+Na] ⁺	605.5 671.5	[SO] ⁺ [DhaO+Na] ⁺	651.5	[DhaS] ⁺
Epa-O-E	C ₆₁ H ₁₀₄ O ₆	955.7	645.5 673.5	[EpaO+Na] ⁺ [EpaE+Na] ⁺	653.5 631.5	[EO+Na] ⁺ [EO] ⁺	623.5 651.5	[EpaO] ⁺ [EpaE] ⁺
Dpa-O-S	C ₆₁ H ₁₀₄ O ₆	957.7	673.5 675.5	[DpaO+Na] ⁺ [DpaS+Na] ⁺	627.5 605.5	[SO+Na] ⁺ [SO] ⁺	651.5 653.5	[DpaO] ⁺ [DpaS] ⁺
O-E ₂ -E	C ₆₁ H ₁₁₀ O ₆	961.8	651.5 629.5	[OE ₂ +Na] ⁺ [OE ₂] ⁺	679.5 657.5	[E ₂ E ₁ +Na] ⁺ [E ₂ E ₁] ⁺	653.5 631.5	[OE+Na] ⁺ [OE] ⁺
O-D-L	C ₆₁ H ₁₁₀ O ₆	961.8	679.5 657.5	[DL+Na] ⁺ [DL] ⁺	681.5 659.5	[OD+Na] ⁺ [OD] ⁺	623.5 601.5	[LO+Na] ⁺ [LO] ⁺
T-P-O	C ₆₁ H ₁₁₄ O ₆	965.8	683.6 661.6	[TP+Na] ⁺ [TP] ⁺	599.5 577.5	[PO+Na] ⁺ [PO] ⁺	709.6 687.6	[TO+Na] ⁺ [TO] ⁺
P-E-D	C ₆₁ H ₁₁₄ O ₆	965.8	627.5 605.5	[PE+Na] ⁺ [PE] ⁺	709.6 687.6	[ED+Na] ⁺ [ED] ⁺	655.6 633.5	[PD+Na] ⁺ [PD] ⁺
B-O-O	C ₆₁ H ₁₁₄ O ₆	965.8	683.6 661.6	[BO+Na] ⁺ [BO] ⁺	625.5 603.5	[OO+Na] ⁺ [OO] ⁺		
Dha-Dha-Po	C ₆₃ H ₉₆ O ₆	971.7	643.5 717.5	[DhaPo+Na] ⁺ [DhaDha+Na] ⁺	621.5	[DhaPo] ⁺	695.5	[DhaDha] ⁺
O-Epa-Dha	C ₆₃ H ₉₈ O ₆	973.7	645.5 691.5	[EpaO+Na] ⁺ [DhaEpa+Na] ⁺	671.5	[DhaO+Na] ⁺	623.5 649.5	[EpaO] ⁺ [DhaO] ⁺
P-Dpa-Dha	C ₆₃ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	975.7	647.5 645.5	[DpaP+Na] ⁺ [DhaP+Na] ⁺	719.5	[DpaDha+Na] ⁺		
Dpa-O-E	C ₆₃ H ₁₀₈ O ₆	983.8	673.5 653.5	[DpaO+Na] ⁺ [OE+Na] ⁺	631.5 701.5	[OE] ⁺ [DpaE+Na] ⁺	679.5 651.5	[DpaE] ⁺ [DpaO] ⁺
S-Epa-D	C ₆₃ H ₁₁₀ O ₆	985.8	647.5 701.5	[SEpa+Na] ⁺ [EpaD+Na] ⁺	683.5	[SD+Na] ⁺		

Table 2: continuation

MS ¹			MS ²					
TAG structure	Formula	Precursor ion [M+Na] ⁺	Major fragments				Minor fragments	
			Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern	Product ion	Fragmentation pattern
E-D-O	C ₆₃ H ₁₁₆ O ₆	991.8	709.6 687.6	[ED+Na] ⁺ [ED] ⁺	681.5 659.5	[OD+Na] ⁺ [OD] ⁺	653.5 631.5	[OE+Na] ⁺ [OE] ⁺
D-Po-D	C ₆₃ H ₁₁₆ O ₆	991.8	653.5 631.5	[PoD+Na] ⁺ [PoD] ⁺			737.6 715.6	[DD+Na] ⁺ [DD] ⁺
Dha-Epa-Epa	C ₆₅ H ₉₄ O ₆	993.7	665.5 691.5	[EpaEpa+Na] ⁺ [DhaEpa+Na] ⁺			643.5 669.5	[EpaEpa] ⁺ [DhaEpa] ⁺
P-E-T	C ₆₅ H ₉₄ O ₆	993.8	627.5 605.5	[PE+Na] ⁺ [PE] ⁺	709.6 687.6	[ET+Na] ⁺ [ET] ⁺	683.6 661.6	[PE+Na] ⁺ [PE] ⁺
Dha-Dha-O	C ₆₅ H ₁₀₀ O ₆	999.7	671.5 717.5	[DhaO+Na] ⁺ [DhaDha+Na] ⁺	649.5	[DhaO] ⁺	695.5	[DhaDha] ⁺
O-Dpa-Dha	C ₆₅ H ₁₀₂ O ₆	1001.7	673.5 671.5	[DpaO+Na] ⁺ [DhaO+Na] ⁺	719.5	[DpaDha+Na] ⁺	653.5	[OE+Na] ⁺
D-Epa-E	C ₆₅ H ₁₁₂ O ₆	1011.8	673.5 701.5	[EpaE+Na] ⁺ [DEpa+Na] ⁺	709.6	[DE+Na] ⁺	651.5 679.5	[EpaE] ⁺ [DEpa] ⁺
Dha-Epa-Dha	C ₆₇ H ₉₆ O ₆	1019.7	691.5 717.5	[DhaEpa+Na] ⁺ [DhaDha+Na] ⁺			669.5 695.5	[DhaEpa] ⁺ [DhaDha] ⁺
O-D-D	C ₆₅ H ₁₂₀ O ₆	1019.8	681.5 659.5	[OD+Na] ⁺ [OD] ⁺	737.6 715.6	[DD+Na] ⁺ [DD] ⁺		
T-O-E	C ₆₅ H ₁₂₀ O ₆	1019.8	653.6 631.6	[OE+Na] ⁺ [OE] ⁺	709.6 687.6	[TO+Na] ⁺ [TO] ⁺	737.6 715.6	[TE+Na] ⁺ [TE] ⁺
Dha-E4-Dha	C ₆₇ H ₉₈ O ₆	1021.7	693.5 717.5	[DhaE4+Na] ⁺ [DhaDha+Na] ⁺			671.5 695.5	[DhaE4] ⁺ [DhaDha] ⁺
E-D-Dha	C ₆₇ H ₁₁₄ O ₆	1037.8	709.6 699.5	[ED+Na] ⁺ [DhaE+Na] ⁺	727.6 687.6	[DhaD+Na] ⁺ [ED] ⁺	705.6 677.5	[DhaD] ⁺ [DhaE] ⁺
D-D-Dha	C ₆₉ H ₁₁₈ O ₆	1065.8	727.6 737.6	[DhaD+Na] ⁺ [DD+Na] ⁺	[DD+Na] ⁺		705.6 715.6	[DhaD] ⁺ [DD] ⁺
D-D-D	C ₆₉ H ₁₂₈ O ₆	1075.9	737.6 715.6	[DD+Na] ⁺ [DD] ⁺				

648 Table 3: TAG ratios calculated for the reference materials and the archaeological samples.

Ratio	Fresh reference materials						Archaeological ceramic samples
	Balaenoptera			Megaptera	Phocoena	Unknown whale oil	
	Sei whale	Fin whale	Minke whale	Humpback whale	Harbour porpoise		
$\frac{\text{LaPO}}{\text{LaPL}}$	1.65	1.87	1.80	0.67	0.36	1.62	1.64
$\frac{\text{PPoO}}{\text{POP}}$	1.10	1.23	1.20	3.02	2.15	1.17	0.82
$\frac{\text{MOP}}{\text{SPoM}}$	1.51	1.49	1.24	0.98	0.54	0.97	1.64
$\frac{\text{MOLa}}{\text{MLaL}}$	3.35	3.64	3.41	3.57	0.20	2.29	2.69

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652 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

653 **Figure 1.** Archaeological ceramic fragments found in a deposit in Lekeitio showing the internal
654 surface of the vessel: a) L002, b) L003, c) L006, d) L016 and e) L020.

655 **Figure 2.** MS² spectra for the PPO.

656 **Figure 3.** MS² spectra for the two possible compounds with the same fragments and parent ion
657 E-D-O and D-Po-D.

658 **Figure 4.** Obtained profiles of TAGs in different whale blubber samples used as reference
659 materials.

660 **Figure 5.** Non polyunsaturated TAGs profiles found in whale blubber and oil samples used as
661 reference material: a) sei whale, b) fin whale, c) minke whale, d) harbour porpoise,
662 e) humpback whale and d) whale oil from unknown origin

663 **Figure 6.** Non polyunsaturated TAGs profiles for the archaeological ceramic samples in
664 comparison with one of the Balaenoptera species (sei whale).

665 **Figure 7.** TIC of the trimethylsilylated acid fraction of sample L016 obtained by GC-MS. Cx:y are
666 fatty acids of chain length x and degree of unsaturation y; diCx are α,ω -dicarboxylic
667 fatty acids of chain length x; 9,10OHC16 is 9,10-dihydroxyhexadecanoic acid;
668 9,10OHC18 is 9,10-dihydroxyoctadecanoic acid; 11,12OHC20 is 11,12-
669 dihydroxyeicosanoic acid; 11,12OHC22 is 11,12-dihydroxydocosanoic acid; TMTD is
670 3,8,12-trimethyltridecanoic acid; Pris is pristanic acid; Phy is phytanic acid.

671 **Figure 8.** Comparison of the FA profile between the fresh reference materials and the
672 archaeological ceramics: a) sample L016 vs. whale species of Balaenoptera genus (sei
673 whale and minke whale) and b) sample L020 vs. Phocoena and Megaptera (harbour
674 porpoise and humpback whale, respectively). Cx:y are fatty acids of chain length x and
675 degree of unsaturation y; diCx are α,ω -dicarboxylic fatty acids of chain length x

a)

b)

c)

d)

e)

Sei whale

Humpback whale

Minke whale

Harbour Porpoise

Fin whale

